

PRISMA Hyperspectral Data Aggregation Techniques for Retrieval of Sentinel-2 Vegetation Indices

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Abstract

Smart agriculture has emerged as a crucial and rapidly growing field, where a deep understanding of data plays a pivotal role. In this paper, we center our analysis on accurate computation of two vegetation indices, namely, the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), using Sentinel-2 (multispectral) and PRISMA (hyperspectral) imagery. Various methods were employed to compute vegetation indices from PRISMA images, which were then evaluated using a similarity measure, with the Sentinel-2 imagery serving as the reference. To enhance the study’s rigor, we focused on specific crops rather than analyzing the entire image. Our findings demonstrate that discrepancies can occur between the indices derived from PRISMA and Sentinel-2 images, particularly during the early vegetative stages of crops. Additionally, we conducted a detailed comparison of the proposed methods for computing vegetation indices in PRISMA hyperspectral images while aiming to retrieve as accurate as possible Sentinel-2 computed values.

Keywords— Remote sensing, NDVI, NDWI, PRISMA, Sentinel-2, Agricultural Monitoring, Precision Agriculture

1 Introduction

Vegetation indices (VI) are quantitative indicators that are derived from remote sensing data to monitor and evaluate the health, biomass, and cover of vegetation [1]. These indices emphasize the distinctive reflectance characteristics of vegetation by employing spe-

cific spectral bands, frequently in the visible, near-infrared (NIR), and shortwave infrared (SWIR) regions. Remote sensing includes two main data types: multispectral (e.g., Landsat, Sentinel) and hyperspectral (e.g., PRISMA). While multispectral data has well-defined bands for vegetation index (VI) computation [2], PRISMA lacks this clarity. This raises the question: how can equivalent hyperspectral bands be identified to match Sentinel values?

In terms of VIs, the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is a widely used remote sensing metric for assessing vegetation health, vigor, and density. Healthy vegetation absorbs most red light (RED) for photosynthesis and reflects a significant portion of near-infrared light (NIR). The Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) [3] monitors vegetation canopy water content by leveraging the reflectance properties of vegetation in the near-infrared (NIR) and shortwave infrared (SWIR) regions, where water-rich vegetation strongly reflects NIR and absorbs SWIR.

The formula for NDVI, and respectively NDWI are as follows:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - RED}{NIR + RED}; \quad NDWI = \frac{NIR - SWIR}{NIR + SWIR} \quad (1)$$

Both have resulting values range from -1 to $+1$. NDVI values near $+1$ indicate dense vegetation, while values near 0 or negative suggest sparse vegetation, bare soil, or non-vegetated surfaces like water or urban areas. High NDWI values indicate greater vegetation water content, while lower or negative values suggest dry vegetation, stressed plants, or non-vegetated areas.

While many other vegetation indices have been proposed [1], they use the same spectral bands and, thus, from a data analysis point of view, conclusions are redundant.

Matching spectral information from hyperspectral to

Figure 1: (a) PRISMA Image ; (b) Sentinel image ; (c) Aligned PRISMA image to Sentinel geometry

Figure 2: (Left) Mask for Sentinel Image ; (Middle) NDVI result for March, (Right) NDVI result for May

multispectral has been approached before. Fusion of two types of data has been attempted with both classical methods [4] as with deep ones [5]; yet the purpose of these methods is to combine data for maximum information and not to compare and match. Other works compared the efficiency of the spectral data to various problems [6], [7] and found an edge for hyperspectral. However, in such comparison, “bad bands” have been found in hyperspectral data [8]. Therefore, the problem of aggregating hyperspectral bands to match the broad ones from multispectral, especially for VI, needs further contributions.

2 Approach

2.1 Data

The image data for this work describes an area in Brasov County, Romania and is associated with public dataset¹ μ -DACIA5 [9].

The multispectral images from the Sentinel-2 (Level 2A), has 13 spectral bands (visible, NIR, and SWIR) with spatial resolutions of 10–60 meters and a 290 km swath. Sentinel-2 offers global coverage every 5 days. Images from 23 March and 14 May 2024 were selected

¹ μ -DACIA5 is available at <https://zenodo.org/records/14283243>

Figure 3: NDVI results for PRISMA in March. (Left) NDVI result for (i) method proposed ; (Middle) NDVI method for (ii) method proposed ; (Right) Heatmap based on SSIM metric for a 7×7 window between Sentinel and PRISMA NDVI image (warm colors means high similarity)

to capture distinct vegetation periods, focusing on early spring crops and later growth stages.

Hyperspectral images from the PRISMA L2C satellite, captures data across 400–2500 nm with 239 hyperspectral bands and a panchromatic band for added resolution [10]. Images from 23 March, 14/19 May, and 18 June 2024 were chosen to observe diverse crops at various growth stages. In Figure 1 we show the RGB color composites the March PRISMA and Sentinel images.

2.2 Geometry Alignment

The geometry of the PRISMA picture differs from that of the Sentinel, requiring a perspective transform for direct image comparison. To determine the needed perspective we used the classical solution [11] based on keypoint localization and feature description. Instead of the classical SIFT [12], the ORB keypoint locator and descriptor [13] was used. The transforming homography is determined using RANSAC [14]. Using the so-found homography matrix, the source image (Sentinel) is warped onto the plane of the target image (PRISMA) via interpolation, correcting perspective differences and aligning the two images. The result can be seen in Figure 1c.

2.3 PRISMA NDVI and NDWI Computation

In multispectral data, the bands needed are clear. NDVI uses B4 (RED) and B8 (NIR) [15], whereas NDWI needs B8A (Narrow NIR) and B11 (SWIR) [3]. PRISMA’s dense sampling makes it harder to establish a clear calculation rule. Here, we investigated 3 strategies:

Table 1: Average SSIM for $\text{NDVI} = f(\text{RED}, \text{NIR})$ between the Sentinel reference and the PRISMA image. **Individual PRISMA bands** are sequentially used - method (i). Orange - Lower values ; Beige-Middle values Yellow - Higher values ; White - Highest value

RED/ NIR Bands	22	21	20	19	18	17	16	15	14	13	12	11
35	0.729	0.724	0.716	0.721	0.710	0.707	0.709	0.706	0.705	0.697	0.693	0.693
34	0.734	0.729	0.722	0.727	0.718	0.714	0.716	0.714	0.713	0.705	0.702	0.702
33	0.735	0.731	0.724	0.729	0.721	0.718	0.719	0.718	0.717	0.709	0.705	0.706
32	0.738	0.736	0.730	0.734	0.727	0.724	0.726	0.724	0.724	0.716	0.713	0.713

Table 2: Average SSIM for $\text{NDWI} = f(\text{narrow NIR}, \text{SWIR})$ between Sentinel and **individual bands** from PRISMA image - method (i)

Narrow NIR/SWIR Bands	112	111	110	109	108	108	106	105	104
16	0.7155	0.7105	0.7173	0.7162	0.7116	0.7066	0.7009	0.6959	0.6684
15	0.7221	0.7174	0.7229	0.7205	0.7147	0.7094	0.7022	0.6966	0.667
14	0.7254	0.7204	0.7264	0.7241	0.7182	0.7125	0.7057	0.7002	0.671
13	0.731	0.733	0.7216	0.7084	0.6955	0.6904	0.6728	0.6616	0.6173

(i) **Individual bands.** The connection between the Sentinel and PRISMA bands was made according to [16]. Thus, the PRISMA bands associated with the Sentinel were the following: RED band (B4 Sentinel) \rightarrow 32-35 (685 - 647 nm), NIR band (B8 Sentinel) \rightarrow 11-22 (905 - 778 nm), Narrow NIR band (B8A Sentinel) \rightarrow 13-16 (880 - 849 nm), SWIR band 11 (B11 Sentinel) \rightarrow 104 - 112 (1654 - 1558 nm).

(ii) The **average** of the PRISMA bands associated with each Sentinel plane. For example, for the NDVI index, the average of the PRISMA red bands and the average of the PRISMA NIR bands were computed.

(iii) The **weighted average** of the PRISMA bands associated with each multispectral plane. The final weighted band can be described as:

$$B_w = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N w_i B_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N w_i} \quad (2)$$

where B_i is one of the PRISMA bands, w_i is the weight for PRISMA band B_i according to Sentinel documentation [17]. N is the number of PRISMA bands corresponding to the Sentinel. For instance, N is 4 for the RED band, RED in PRISMA is described by 4 bands.

Table 3: Average SSIM for the 3 computation methods proposed for NDVI and NDWI indices in March and June . Orange - Lower values ; Beige-Middle values Yellow - Highest value

Method/Month	NDVI		NDWI	
	March	May	March	May
Individual bands (i)	0.7376	0.7208	0.733	0.6498
Average (ii)	0.7165	0.7011	0.7173	0.6255
Weighted Average (iii)	0.7195	0.7053	0.7176	0.6357

3 Experimental Results

In this section we will present the results obtained with the 3 methods mentioned above for the selected VIs. Images containing vegetation indices for Sentinel and PRISMA can be compared visually in most cases. However, to get a broader idea of the differences between them, we used the Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) [18].

We chose SSIM over other metrics because it reflects human visual perception by evaluating brightness, contrast, and structural (pattern) similarity [18] — key factors in picture quality assessment. In contrast, pixel-wise metrics like MSE, MAE, and PSNR quantify absolute discrepancies but overlook perceptual relevance, treating critical structural errors the same as minor differences in less significant areas.

Figure 2 (middle and right) shows the NDVI results

Figure 4: The statistic parameters for 3 crops in May for NDVI. Red color - NDVI standard deviations for PRISMA and Sentinel crop regions. Green color - NDVI averages for PRISMA and Sentinel crop regions. Purple - Average SSIM for each crop.

Figure 5: Comparison between first and second method for NDWI. $\mu_1, \mu_2, \sigma_1, \sigma_2$ are the crop NDWI averages and standard deviations for PRISMA image using first and second technique. μ_R, σ_R are the NDWI average and standard deviation for the Sentinel image. SSIM1 and SSIM2 are the similarity results for the first and second technique for every crop.

for the Sentinel image in March and May, with the crop mask represented on the left. Figure 3 (left and middle) displays the NDVI results for March using methods (i) and (ii), while the right shows the SSIM heatmap for a 7×7 window comparing Sentinel and PRISMA NDVI images. Overall, the similarity is high (warm colors), except in the upper-right corner, where smaller parcels with mixed crops reduce accuracy. Noticing that parcel size matters, we calculated SSIM for various window sizes: from 3×3 to 9×9 . A 3×3 window covers 60×60 meters. Larger windows may encompass smaller fields, but we also aimed to assess broader similarity levels.

Using individual bands, leads to results from Tables 1 and 2. Both indices show strong similarity values, indicating a high correlation between the PRISMA bands. The optimal similarity for both indices occurs at longer wavelengths for the red/narrow NIR band and shorter wavelengths for the NIR/SWIR band. For NDVI, the best combination is RED 35 and NIR 22, while for NDWI, it is Narrow NIR 13 and SWIR 111.

Table 3 compares the SSIM metric for the three investigated methods. The individual bands technique

shows slightly better matching, but the differences are minimal. For further insights, we analyzed specific crops across different months for both VIs. Table 4 presents SSIM results for various window sizes (beige columns), average SSIM (red column), and averages and standard deviations for individual crops in both Sentinel and PRISMA images (green columns). Only the individual bands method (i) and the global average method (ii) were considered, as the third option (iii) showed similar results to (ii).

We selected the most frequent crops based on pixel count in the Sentinel image: *spring wheat*, *peas*, *potatoes*, *sugarbeet*, and *corn*. Some crops, like *potatoes*, *sugarbeet*, and *corn*, were not yet sprouted in May and were classified as *bare soil*. Initially, method (i) showed slightly better results than method (ii) for the NDVI index, but the differences were more apparent for NDWI. Adding supplementary bands can cause spectral mixing, leading to discrepancies from the original Sentinel NDWI measurements, as the weights may not accurately replicate the Sentinel spectral response.

In Figure 4, red and green highlight the averages and standard deviations for selected crops from PRISMA and Sentinel images, and purple marks the average SSIM. Comparing *peas* with *spring wheat*, the SSIM for *wheat* is slightly improved, though the average difference remains similar. *Peas* show worse similarity due to higher variance (red columns), which impacts the SSIM contrast component. *Bare soil* results are even worse, despite similar standard deviations, due to a higher bias between the averages (green columns).

For *potato* and *sugarbeet* crops, the similarity improves with larger window sizes for both methods (Rows 4-5; 9-10 in Table 4). This is likely because these crops are in early growth stages, where uneven development causes higher variability within parcels. Larger windows reduce this variability, leading to better results. However, for crops in more advanced stages, similarity decreases as window size increases, a pattern seen in both NDVI and NDWI.

In the second part of Table 4 for the NDWI index, similarity results for the individual bands method (i) are generally better than the average method (ii) for most crops. Figure 5 illustrates why. Red highlights the differences in standard deviations between the crops in the PRISMA image for methods (i) and (ii) compared to the Sentinel image. Green shows the average differences, and purple indicates the similarity difference between the two methods. For *potato* and *sugarbeet*, the similarity difference between methods (i) and (ii) is greater than for *spring wheat*. Notably, method (ii) consistently yields higher crop averages than Sentinel, leading to a larger green column. However, the standard deviation plays a key role: when the gap in stan-

standard deviations is larger (red columns more uneven), the SSIM difference increases (purple column higher). This affects the *potato* crop more, while *spring wheat* shows less influence due to similar standard deviations. These results show that the covariance and contrast components of SSIM, based on standard deviations, have more influence than brightness, based on averages, in the final results.

4 Conclusions

In this article, we proposed a analysis of the NDVI and NDWI vegetation indices values derived for Sentinel-2 multispectral images and PRISMA hyperspectral images. Given the multitude of bands in hyperspectral data, we examined three variants for computing the

vegetation indices through various PRISMA individual bands or their weighted averages. To compare the results obtained, we used a similarity metric entitled Structure Similarity Index Measure (SSIM).

The results show a strong correlation between neighboring bands in the hyperspectral domain, as the similarity between vegetation indices from PRISMA and Sentinel-2 increased for most individual band combinations. This is primarily due to the more favorable vegetation index results from average-based variations.

The technique using the optimal mix of individual bands is often slightly better than the averaging methods. For the NDWI index, the first method significantly outperforms the others, especially for crops in early vegetation stages. This suggests that adding extra bands may cause spectral mixing, leading to deviations from

Table 4: SSIM results for NDVI and NDWI for some particular crops. The results are reported for different window sizes when computing SSIM (yellow columns). There are also reported the averages and standard deviations for every studied crop for PRISMA and Sentinel image (green columns). The red column is the average SSIM for all the window sizes

. “AS” stands for Average SSIM, “StP” stands for “Standard deviation PRIS”, “StS” for “Standard deviation Sent”, “AvP” for “Average PRIS”, “AvS” for “Average Sent”

Meth.	Idx	Crop/ Month	NDVI								
			Window size					Crop NDVI Avg/Std			
			3 × 3	5 × 5	7 × 7	9 × 9	AS	StP	StS	AvP	AvS
Bands	1	Spring Wheat - May	0.935	0.906	0.887	0.875	0.901	0.085	0.088	0.941	0.888
	2	Peas -May	0.871	0.846	0.839	0.839	0.849	0.060	0.028	0.894	0.834
	3	Bear Soil - May	0.762	0.739	0.732	0.737	0.743	0.133	0.135	0.334	0.262
	4	Potato - June	0.857	0.872	0.885	0.897	0.879	0.205	0.202	0.574	0.533
	5	Sugarbeat - June	0.762	0.765	0.781	0.796	0.776	0.105	0.120	0.605	0.556
Average	6	Spring Wheat - May	0.935	0.905	0.884	0.870	0.898	0.077	0.088	0.947	0.878
	7	Peas -May	0.883	0.861	0.856	0.856	0.864	0.052	0.018	0.895	0.834
	8	Bear Soil - May	0.7104	0.6916	0.688	0.695	0.696	0.126	0.135	0.402	0.262
	9	Potato - June	0.838	0.846	0.857	0.868	0.853	0.189	0.202	0.616	0.533
	10	Sugarbeat - June	0.756	0.755	0.768	0.781	0.765	0.095	0.120	0.636	0.556
Meth.	Idx	Crop	NDWI								
			Window size					Crop NDWI Avg/Std			
			3 × 3	5 × 5	7 × 7	9 × 9	AS	StP	StS	AvP	AvS
Bands	11	Spring Wheat - June	0.826	0.8024	0.804	0.812	0.811	0.087	0.070	0.246	0.199
	12	Peas - June	0.866	0.845	0.839	0.839	0.847	0.049	0.039	0.299	0.225
	13	Sugarbeat - June	0.794	0.804	0.813	0.820	0.807	0.109	0.097	0.102	0.076
	14	Potato - June	0.836	0.844	0.850	0.858	0.847	0.033	0.029	0.240	0.228
	15	Bear Soil - June	0.828	0.832	0.834	0.835	0.833	0.118	0.091	-0.036	-0.052
Average	16	Spring Wheat - June	0.805	0.784	0.784	0.788	0.790	0.088	0.070	0.275	0.199
	17	Peas - June	0.843	0.822	0.815	0.814	0.824	0.050	0.039	0.327	0.225
	18	Sugarbeat- June	0.717	0.724	0.730	0.734	0.726	0.120	0.097	0.131	0.076
	19	Potato-June	0.655	0.683	0.705	0.749	0.698	0.059	0.029	0.270	0.228
	20	Bear Soil - June	0.730	0.728	0.729	0.727	0.729	0.118	0.092	-0.012	-0.052

the true Sentinel NDWI values. The weights may not fully replicate the Sentinel spectral response, resulting in mismatches. This is also observed for non-vegetative components, such as *bare soil*, where individual bands show higher similarity than their mean.

Acknowledgment

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This work was funded by the European Union. AI4AGRI project entitled “Romanian Excellence Center on Artificial Intelligence on Earth Observation Data for Agriculture” received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant GA no. 101079136.

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